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Cyclic reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry in the study of electrochemical mechanisms

Nataliya Karaush-Karmazin*, Helen Lut, Rostislav Galagan and Boris Minaev

Department of Chemistry and Nanomaterials Science, Bohdan Khmelnytsky National University, Cherkasy, 18031, Ukraine.

ABSTRACT

We report on the development of the cyclic reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry (CRDC) method with controlled alternating current to investigate the mechanisms of rapid electrochemical reactions. The proposed approach is based on the use of alternating current of industrial frequency. To obtain the $E-t$ response, we used a scheme which includes an electric chain consisting of a germanium diode and an adjustable source of constant voltage being parallel to the sensor electrodes. Digital analysis of the primary data allows us to obtain the following signal transformants: $dE/dt-E$, $dt/dE-E$, $dq/dE-E$, $I-E$. Such an approach permits to observe the structurization of the response, which can be associated with the process stages. The modified CRDC method was applied to the oxidation of catechol and pyrocatechin violet dye on platinum microelectrodes and to the reduction of camphor, methionine, and methylene blue dye on a mercury dropping electrode. It was found that the anodic oxidation of catechol and its derivatives is accompanied by the peak structurization exhibited on the C_d-E dependences, indicating a two-stage process, while the C_d-E dependence of the pyrocatechin violet dye molecule, containing a catechol core, did not show any peak structurization. This can be explained by one-electron oxidation process with formation of a radical, which is similar to the Gomberg's triphenylmethyl radical. This conclusion is also confirmed by our results

of density functional theory (DFT) calculations for the corresponding dye, radical and dimer. The C_d-E dependence for camphor indicates the reaction-desorption EC mechanism. For methylene blue the cathode peak of very narrow half-width was obtained, which determines the dye aggregation and formation of dye nanophase on the mercury surface.

KEYWORDS: alternating current, reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry, pyrocatechol violet dye, DFT calculations, electrochemical mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

The cyclic derivative chronopotentiometry method with alternating current originates from the "oscillographic polarography" proposed by J. Heyrovský in 1941 [1]. This method has several advantages compared to classical polarography: namely, a short time of one measurement, simultaneous fixation of both the cathode and anode processes, which allows to make a conclusion about the reaction reversibility, the possibility of adsorption processes investigating, since the dE/dt signal is inversely proportional to the total differential capacitance (C_d), as well as this method allows an experiment to be carried out without removing the oxygen from the test solution. However, along with definite advantages, the most significant disadvantage of this method is connected with a low sensitivity at the concentration level of 10^{-4} mol/dm³ [2], which prevents application of this method to processes with a delayed electrochemical stage. Another disadvantage of the method is that the increasing

*Corresponding author: karaush22@ukr.net

depolarizer concentration leads to a nonlinearity of the calibration curve.

In the 80s of the last century it was proposed to register the signal as an inverse derivative $(dE/dt)^{-1} = f(E)$, while the current strength value was set as a constant [3]. This method has been called reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry (RDC). In such embodiment this method is widely used today, especially in biochemical studies [4-6]. The application of alternating current allowed to make this method a cyclical one. This method is called the cyclic reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry (CRDC) [7-10]. A significant number of theoretical works are devoted to application of electric current being set by various functions of time [11-13].

In our studies the CRDC method is implemented by application of sinusoidal current with industrial frequency (50 Hz). The applied program provides continuous recording of the electrode potential and its numerical differentiation. The program divides the alternating current period into 512 time slots with duration of $3.90625 \cdot 10^{-5}$ s. Approximate value of the derivative dE/dt is obtained by dividing the potential difference at the beginning and at the end of each discrete slot by its duration. Thus, the temporarily used program provides data only for the $dE/dt-E$ dependence. Therefore, the proposed development of this method involves conversion of the inverse derivative of this function to the transformant C_d vs potential. This means that the inverse derivative of the function must be multiplied by the increment of the current strength in each time discrete.

In this paper we have used the modified CRDC method to study the oxidation/reduction processes for a number of organic compounds (catechol, pyrocatechin violet dye, camphor, methionine and methylene blue dye). The complex application of the differential capacitance C_d vs potential and

dE/dt dependencies made it possible to draw conclusions about the mechanism of electrode processes for the first two compounds, adsorption phenomena on the electrodes for the second ones and formation of nanophase for the latter compound.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The background solutions, 1.0 M HCl (reagent grade) and 1.0 M NaOH (reagent grade) were prepared with bidistilled water. Catechol, pyrocatechin violet, camphor, methionine and methylene blue dye were received from Sigma-Aldrich. To obtain chronopotentiometric dependencies, we have used the device based on a scheme which includes an electric chain consisting of germanium diode and an adjustable source of regulated constant voltage being parallel to the sensor electrodes (Fig. 1) [14]. The voltage from the sensor electrodes enters to the first ADA channel (12 bit ADA) of the E14-140 type produced by L-CARD, and the voltage drop on the calibrated resistor R_2 switched on in the serial connection to the electrodes circuit enters to the second channel. The dE/dt vs E dependence was obtained in the Polarostydio-2006 program [15] which made it possible to display the graph on the screen and store the data in a text file. The amplitude of the alternating current and phase displacement between current strength and potential were recorded using an oscilloscope SDS1102 of the OWON Company. The current strength was calculated by the standard formula

$$I(t) = I_a \cdot \sin(\omega t + \varphi), \quad (1)$$

where I_a – amplitude value of the alternating current, φ – phase displacement between current strength and potential.

The total differential capacity was calculated according to the equation:

$$C_d = \frac{dq}{dE} = \left(\frac{dE}{dt}\right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\Delta I}{A} = \left(\frac{dE}{dt}\right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\Delta I_a}{A} \cdot (\sin(\omega t_i + \varphi) - \sin(\omega t_{i+t} + \varphi)), \quad (2)$$

where A – the electrode area.

The voltammetric measurements were performed using a PA2 Polarographic Analyzer (Laboratorní přístroje, Praha).

A special feature of the working electrode used in this polarization scheme is that it should have a small area. Therefore, the used electrode was prepared by melting a piece of platinum wire of diameter

Fig. 1. Simplified scheme of the chronopotentiometric set; T – transformer providing galvanic isolation from the network; R_1 is a multi-sectional variable resistor for controlling the current through electrodes; R_2 is a calibrated resistor, in which voltage drop is proportional to the current in a circuit; D is a semiconductor germanium diode in series with which the source of smoothly regulated voltage is included; V – high impedance voltmeter for controlling the initial potential of the electrode polarization.

0.5 mm into the glass tube with subsequent grinding of the end face.

Mercury droplet electrode in the CRDC method should not work continuously, because it should be enough to generate a series of 2–3 mercury droplets. Thus, we can record hundreds of polarization electrode cycles on each drop during its lifetime. The program allows to scroll through the records to select the desired polarization interval. Fig. 2 shows a schematic drawing of this electrode, which comprises a polarographic capillary attached to a medical syringe of 1.0 ml, in the lower part of which a platinum wire is introduced for contact with mercury, and there is an air space between the mercury surface and the piston. The generation of a droplets series is induced by the increased air pressure upon pushing the piston. The whole construction is placed in a protective case made of a piece of thick-walled polyethylene tube [16].

The molecular structures of the homocysteine (HC), pyrocatechin violet dye (PV) and its intermediate oxidation products were optimized at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of the density functional theory (DFT) [17-20] using the Gaussian 16 package [21]. Calculation of the molecular structures of pyrocatechin violet radicals (PVR1, PVR2) and homocysteine radical (HCR) in the ground doublet state was carried out by the spin unrestricted UB3LYP method with the same basis

Fig. 2. The mercury droplet electrode: 1 – glass capillary; 2 – medical syringe of 1.0 ml; 3 – platinum contact with a soldered copper conductor; 4 – the protective case.

set. The convergence criterion for all studied species is fulfilled with the attainment of a stationary point. All calculated vibrational wavenumbers were found to be real. This indicates the location of a true minimum on the hypersurface of the total energy for all studied systems.

Fig. 3. $C_d-f(E)$ dependences of 0.01 M catechol solution on Pt electrode in 1.0 M HCl solution (*a* – dE/dt dependences, *b* – the phase pattern, 1 – background 1.0 M HCl solution, 2 – catechol solution).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CRDC method was used to study the anodic oxidation processes of the catechol and pyrocatechin violet (PV) dye on the platinum microelectrode and the cathodic reduction processes of camphor, methionine and methylene blue dye on the mercury droplet electrode which is described above.

3.1. Anodic processes

3.1.1. Catechol

Fig. 3 shows the $C_d - E$ dependence of 0.01 M catechol solution on Pt electrode in 1.0 M HCl in comparison with the data of cyclic derivative chronopotentiometry (insert *a* in Fig. 3) at a frequency of 50 Hz. It was found that upon

oxidation of catechol, there is the peak structuring which corresponds to the anodic oxidation process in the $C_d = f(E)$ dependence (Fig. 3). It should be noted that the structurization of peak is not observed in the voltammetry curve (insert *b* in Fig. 3). In our opinion, the great peak structure in Fig. 3 is responsible for certain stages of the electrode process. Really, the first one-electron stage of the catechol oxidation process corresponds to formation of a radical, which loses another electron in the second stage, becoming orthoquinone. Similar behavior is also characteristic of other phenolic compounds, in particular, alizarin and adrenaline [see SI, Ref. 15].

The catechol oxidation process is presented by the following scheme:

Thus, a simple operation of the derivative inversion allows to discover additional information which is contained in the primary data in the implicit form. As one can see from Fig. 3, the peak structuring does not manifest itself in the dependence obtained by the traditional cyclic voltammetry method. The same pattern is observed in the cyclic derivative chronopotentiometry at a frequency of 50 Hz. The transition to $C_d = f(E)$ transformant is important in terms of physical chemistry of fast electrode process investigation. It should be noted that the differential capacitance value (C_d) obtained in this way represents the sum of two components: the electrical double-layer capacitance (EDLC) and the pseudocapacity of the Faraday's process on the electrode.

3.1.2. Pyrocatechol violet dye (PV)

Behavior of the PV dye, whose molecule contains the catechol core, is different from the previously discussed behavior of the catechol molecule. First of all, the structuring of the anodic peak (0.67 V) is not observed (Fig. 4). This indicates that the pyrocatechin core is not a reaction center in this case. We assume that the one-stage **electrochemical (EC)** oxidation process of pyrocatechol violet dye proceeds through formation of the PVR1 radical

(Fig. 5) which is similar to the triphenylmethyl radical [22-24] with its subsequent dimerization.

Our DFT calculations indicate that the proton can easily cleave from the PV dye molecule during the first stage (the bond disociation energy is only $94.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) with the formation of a PVR1 radical. The simultaneous detachment of two protons, which can occur by the proposed pathways (2) and (3) is a more energy-consuming process (169.1 and $162.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ for pathways (2) and (3), respectively). The properties of the PVR1 radical must be similar to those of the triphenylmethyl radical proposed by Gomberg *et al.* [22-24]. Thus, the PVR1 must exist in equilibrium with its dimer (DMR).

Our DFT calculations predict that the atoms C1 and C2 of the PVR1 radical represent the most concentrated spin density localization centers for π electron (0.482 and 0.401 at the C1 and C2 atoms, respectively). Thus, the dimeric structure (DMR) can occur through the C1 and C2 atoms' link with

Fig. 4. $C_d=f(E)$ dependences of 0.008 M pyrocatechol violet solution on Pt electrode in 1.0 M HCl (a – dE/dt dependences, b – the phase pattern, 1 – background 1.0 M HCl solution, 2 – pyrocatechol violet solution).

Fig. 5. The structure of the PV and intermediate products of its oxidation.

formation of an elongated C–C bond length of 1.64 Å (Fig. 5). The low stability of such radicals is supposed to be explained by the steric complications of the recombination reaction (4) [25].

3.2. Cathodic processes

3.2.1. Camphor

The reduction process of camphor was investigated on the supporting 1 M NaOH solution. The CRDC dependence in the coordinates “capacitance – potential”, dE/dt , as well as the phase pattern of the process are shown in Fig. 6. The camphor molecules are adsorbed on the electrode surface in the interval of potentials from -0.7 to -1.35 V (insert *b* in Fig. 6). At potential more negative than -1.35 V, the reduction process of camphor to the cyclic alcohol (borneol) begins; the latter is not adsorbed on mercury drop as it is seen from the insert *b* in Fig. 6. The corresponding curves for the depolarizer and for the background solution do coincide. Borneol molecules quickly leave the reaction zone and diffuse

into solution. This determines the rapid growth of the capacitance (C_d) up to its peak value. At the anode branch, there is a peak of borneol oxidation, whose molecules have not been diffused yet into a deep solution. We have also observed the camphor adsorption on the electrode surface as evidenced by the output of the depolarizer curve beyond the curve of the background solution. Thus, the reduction process of camphor on the mercury drop has the reaction-desorption electrochemical nature.

3.2.2. Methionine

Electrode behavior of methionine on the mercury electrode is very similar to the camphor behavior (Fig. 7). In particular, the reduction process of methionine is also characterized by a reaction-desorption character. The process of methionine reduction starts at a potential of -0.98 V (insert *b* in Fig. 7), and the maximum of C_d is observed at the potential -1.21 V, indicating that the stage of this process has slowed down. The process can be expressed as follows:

Fig. 6. $C_d-f(E)$ dependences of 0.01 M camphor solution on Hg electrode in 1.0 M NaOH solution (*a* – the phase pattern, *b* – dE/dt dependences, 1 – background 1.0 M NaOH solution, 2 – camphor).

Fig. 7. $C_d-f(E)$ dependences of 0.01 M methionine solution on Hg electrode in 1.0 M NaOH solution (*a* – the phase pattern, *b* – dE/dt dependences, 1 – background 1.0 M NaOH solution, 2 – methionine).

The anodic peak on the CRDC curve corresponds to the homocysteine oxidation with further production of a dimeric structure with the disulfide bond, as shown in the scheme below. Really, our DFT calculations indicate that the proton is easily cleaved from the homocysteine molecule (HC) with formation of the homocysteine radical HCR

(the bond dissociation energy is only 88.4 kcal mol⁻¹). For the HCR radical the π spin density is concentrated mostly at the S atom (0.993) indicating its extremely high reactivity. Our DFT calculations predict the dimer formation through the spin density localization center (S atom) with the S–S bond length of 2.08 Å which is typical for the disulfide bond.

3.2.3. Methylene blue dye (MB)

This dye belongs to the phenothiazine series and is characterized by a high adsorption ability. Therefore, to obtain the $C_{dl}(E)$ dependencies we have used a solution with a rather small concentration ($5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/dm³). An interesting feature of the

dE/dt dependence curves is that the background solution dependence almost coincides with the curve obtained for the depolarizer solution (insert *a* in Fig. 8, outside the regions which correspond to the reduction/oxidation processes). This observation leads to the conclusion that the adsorption of the

Fig. 8. $C_{dl}(E)$ dependences of 0.01 M methylene blue solution on Hg electrode in 1.0 M NaOH solution (*a* – the phase pattern, *b* – dE/dt dependences, 1 – background 1.0 M NaOH solution, 2 – methylene blue dye).

MB dye does not affect the thickness of the EDL. This is possible when the monomolecular layer of adsorbed molecules is formed on the metal surface in such a way that the adsorbed molecules being almost planar adjoin the electrode surface by its entire plane. At the same time, the cathodic peak

has a very small half-width, which is characteristic of the nanophase according to Ref. [26].

Therefore, we assume that the reduction of the MB dye to the leuco form takes place in one two-electron stage according to the following scheme:

4. CONCLUSION

We developed the cyclic reciprocal derivative chronopotentiometry method by applying the sinusoidal alternating current and transformation of the $(dE/dt)^{-1}$ into dq/dE . In order to test it we applied CRDC method to study the anodic oxidation processes of the catechol and pyrocatechin violet dye and also the cathodic reduction processes of camphor, methionine and methylene blue dye. In particular, CRDC modification allows to observe the peak structurization in the C_d - E dependence of catechol, indicating the intermediate stage of the radical formation upon oxidation processes which is not observed in the traditional cyclic voltammetry and in the cyclic derivative chronopotentiometry method. In contrast, the pyrocatechin violet dye does not manifest the peak structurization in the C_d - E dependence, although its molecule also contains a catechol core. This fact is explained by the pyrocatechin violet radical formation (which is similar to the Gomberg's triphenylmethyl radical) and by further formation of dimeric structure upon radicals recombination. This conclusion is in a good agreement with our results of DFT calculations. In the case of reduction processes, the CRDC method indicates the reaction-desorption EC mechanism for camphor and methionine, as well as aggregation and formation of nanophase for the methylene blue dye.

It should be noted that nine years ago the cyclic chronopotentiometry was provided by the PalmSens instruments. But nowadays such a type of technique is not implemented in the modern version of PalmSens apparatus. The presented development

illustrates the unique ability of CRDC in elucidation of latent stages of EC processes; thus, one can hope that our work would initiate a renovating step toward the inclusion of cyclic chronopotentiometry with reciprocal derivative variant into the commercial electrochemical instrumentation.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

There are no conflicts of interest.

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